

Securing IoT: Unveiling Attacks with Multiview-Multitask Learning

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Abstract—With the rapid expansion and use of day-to-day Internet of Things (IoT) applications, cybercriminals are exploiting an increasingly wide attack surface and are capable of executing many successful attacks, leading to significant losses for individuals and organizations. The existing defense mechanisms often rely on single-view, single-task models that utilize a single feature set to perform one specific task. However, modern IoT systems are multifaceted, heterogeneous, and resource-constrained, posing considerable challenges for developing unified and scalable defense solutions. To address this, we propose a novel hybrid model called M²VT that integrates Multi-View Learning (MVL) and Multi-Task Learning (MTL) for effective cyber-attack defense. The model simultaneously processes three distinct subsets of relevant features (views) to perform three interrelated tasks: attack detection, attack category classification, and attack type classification. The model leverages Autoencoder (AE) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks to extract task-specific spatial and temporal features, enhancing both efficiency and cost-effectiveness. The M²VT model is evaluated using four publicly available IoT benchmark datasets and one testbed dataset. Across all tasks and datasets, the model achieves over 96% accuracy, consistently outperforming state-of-the-art approaches. The parallel execution of MVL and MTL, combined with task-specific feature subsets, significantly boosts performance. The implementation of M²VT is publicly available in our code repository¹.

Impact Statement—The proposed M²VT model has significant impacts in unveiling IoT attacks, categories, and types through parallel execution of MVL and MTL. This parallel learning strategy makes M²VT both accurate and cost-effective. The approach provides a robust and impactful defense against IoT vulnerabilities, achieving up to 100% detection accuracy and a detection speed three times faster than existing methods, making it suitable for real-time deployment.

Index Terms—IoT, Multi-view learning, Multi-task learning, Autoencoder, LSTM, Network traffic.

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¹<https://github.com/3Clinton/MVMTL>

I. INTRODUCTION

THE Internet of Things (IoT) has experienced rapid growth due to its wide range of applications and daily uses that impact nearly every aspect of day-to-day life. However, the increasing number of connected devices in IoT networks, coupled with their inherent vulnerabilities, has made them attractive targets for cybercriminals. These adversaries exploit IoT systems for various malicious purposes, including botnet formation, data theft, ransomware attacks, spamming, and cryptojacking [1]. Such cyber-attacks can lead to severe consequences, including financial losses, data breaches, service disruptions, and violations of privacy for both individuals and organizations [2]. The heterogeneity of devices and networks, along with resource constraints, poses significant challenges for conventional defense systems in addressing emerging IoT-specific threats [3], [4]. This necessitates the development of lightweight and adaptive security solutions capable of protecting IoT infrastructures. To this end, researchers have proposed intrusion detection systems (IDS), intrusion prevention systems (IPS), and intrusion mitigation systems (IMS), utilizing statistical methods, machine learning (ML), and deep learning (DL) techniques to address them.

While ML and DL models have shown promise, their effectiveness heavily depends on the quality and representation of the data used for training. Traditional ML approaches require manual feature engineering, whereas DL models can automatically learn hierarchical representations from raw data. To improve model performance and efficiency, various techniques such as feature extraction, feature selection, and dimensionality reduction are employed to derive informative and relevant input features. Although classical ML methods generally incur lower computational costs, DL approaches are often preferred due to their superior ability to handle large-scale data and automatically extract both spatial and temporal patterns. In particular, deep learning has demonstrated strong performance in applications like network traffic classification, anomaly detection, and network optimization [5]. Among DL architectures, Autoencoders (AEs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have proven effective for processing IoT data. Autoencoders are neural networks designed to compress input data into a lower-dimensional representation and reconstruct it, preserving essential information. They are widely used for dimensionality reduction, anomaly detection, and data denoising. Compared to traditional methods such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), AEs are more flexible and capable of capturing non-linear relationships in data, albeit

at a higher computational cost. LSTM networks, a variant of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), are specifically designed to handle sequential data and extract temporal dependencies. They effectively address long-term dependencies in time-series data and mitigate the vanishing gradient problem, making them highly suitable for analyzing dynamic IoT network behavior.

Although conventional single-view, single-task deep learning (DL) models are inspired by the human learning process, they fall short of truly replicating it. Biologically, humans can accurately recognize or classify objects by observing them from multiple perspectives or based on diverse perceptions. Furthermore, humans often perform tasks more efficiently by leveraging knowledge gained from related or similar tasks. To approximate this level of cognitive capability, Multi-View Learning (MVL) and Multi-Task Learning (MTL) have emerged as effective paradigms. MVL enables models to learn from multiple views or feature sets, while MTL allows for the simultaneous learning of multiple related tasks. These approaches not only enhance model performance but also reduce computational overhead compared to conventional DL models. The concepts of MVL and MTL, as well as their integration in our approach to uncover IoT attacks through behavioral network traffic analysis, are detailed in Sections III-A and III-B.

In this paper, we propose a novel lightweight and hybrid attack detection system for IoT networks that leverages Multi-View Learning (MVL) and Multi-Task Learning (MTL). The system utilizes task-specific subsets of relevant features as distinct views, allowing the construction of a more generalized model that benefits from shared information across multiple tasks and concurrently performs multiple tasks: attack detection, attack category classification, and attack types classification. To enhance performance, the system incorporates an Autoencoder (AE) to extract spatial features and reduce input dimensionality, as well as a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network for capturing temporal dependencies in sequential data.

Over the past decades, numerous intelligent attack detection and mitigation systems have been developed for IoT networks, utilizing statistical methods, machine learning (ML), and deep learning (DL) techniques. However, most existing systems rely on a single set of features to perform a specific task—either attack detection or classification. Due to the heterogeneous nature of IoT network traffic, selecting a unified feature set for such tasks remains a significant challenge. Moreover, designing a lightweight system that can detect and classify attacks concurrently while maintaining high performance is still an open issue. Although some existing approaches incorporate Multi-View Learning (MVL) or Multi-Task Learning (MTL) individually, to the best of our knowledge, no prior work has integrated both MVL and MTL for securing IoT networks against cyber-attacks. The proven effectiveness of Autoencoders (AEs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, MVL, and MTL in various application domains inspired us to develop a hybrid smart attack detection system that combines all these techniques. By leveraging MVL and MTL, the system can utilize multiple feature sets to perform multiple tasks concurrently, enhancing the model's generalization and

improving performance in detecting and classifying cyber-attacks. Furthermore, the integration of AE and LSTM enables the extraction of meaningful spatial representations and the capture of temporal dependencies, further boosting the model's effectiveness.

The key contributions of this work are as follows:

- 1) To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to leverage both Multi-View Learning (MVL) and Multi-Task Learning (MTL) to detect cyber-attacks by analyzing network-wide IoT traffic behaviors.
- 2) We propose a hybrid model called M^2VT that utilizes multiple feature sets (views) to perform multiple tasks concurrently: attack detection, attack category classification, and attack type classification in IoT network traffic.
- 3) The model employs a wrapper-based feature selection method to identify task-relevant features, which are treated as separate views. Autoencoders (AEs) are used on each view to extract spatial features and reduce dimensionality. A shared Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) layer then captures temporal dependencies across tasks. By combining the output of each AE with the shared LSTM, the model performs all tasks concurrently and efficiently.
- 4) The proposed M^2VT model is evaluated using four publicly available benchmark IoT datasets and a real-time testbed dataset, and compared with state-of-the-art approaches. The M^2VT model outperforms all baseline models, achieving up to 1.45% higher accuracy than the best-performing state-of-the-art method.

II. RELATED WORK

Developing network intrusion detection and prevention systems for securing IoT environments from cyber-attacks has been a topic of significant interest in recent years. Many detection and prevention of emerging cyber-attacks based on statistical, ML, DL, and hybrid approaches are found in the literature. Moreover, DL-based multi-view learning methods have gained popularity in handling various problems like intrusion detection, text classification, 3D reconstruction, facial detection, and human activity recognition [6]. Similarly, multi-task learning methods are also found to be very effective in the applications of computer vision, bioinformatics, health informatics, speech, NLP, web, and so on [7], [8]. Next, we discuss both multi-view and multi-task learning approaches used for IoT network traffic analysis.

A. MVL-based approaches

Rather than a long feature vector used in the conventional DL approaches, He et al. [9] consider three different levels of features from network data, such as basic (attributes based on protocol connection), content (attributes of the payload information), and traffic (attributes based on connection time). The authors incorporated these features to develop an MVL model called MS-DHPN, which can detect intrusions in a conventional network. MS-DHPN consists of two layers: a multimodal DAE (MDAE) to integrate the complex features in each traffic flow at the low level and an LSTM layer to

extract the temporal information between traffic flows at the high level. Their experimental results show the dominance of the MVL approach over the single-view approach on the NSL-KDD, UNSW-NB15, and CICIDS-2017 datasets. Training a model with a single view may result in perceiving incomplete knowledge of patterns in large features of a dataset. Moreover, the conventional model's training approaches work in a centralized manner that receives data from multiple edge nodes. This centralized storage might result in serious breaches in data privacy and security.

Attota et al. [10] developed an IDS based on federated learning (FL) with ensemble MVL called MV-FLID. The model used multiple views of IoT network data during the model's training in a decentralized approach. They employ the ensemble MVL and FL to maximize the learning efficiency of different attack types and to preserve data privacy. The experiment is carried out on the MQTTset dataset, extracting three views, i.e., packet view, uniflow view, and biflow view, using the Integrating Grey Wolves Optimization mechanism. Their result shows the effectiveness of FL with MVL over the single view and centralized training approach. In addition, MVL has been used to detect malware attacks [11], phishing websites on the internet [12], and attacks in industrial control systems [13]. Although the MVL has been used in many application domains, it is still early in the domain of IoT cybersecurity.

B. MTL-based approaches

Sajid Ali et al. [14] propose an MTL model for detecting malware in an IoT environment. The model incorporates an LSTM to perform malware detection as task 1 and identification of malware types as task 2. They performed a time-series analysis on the packets of network traffic flows containing both normal and malicious traffic collected from 18 IoT devices. Moreover, they extracted features from the raw network traffic data and grouped them into three categories, i.e., packet payload-related, flow-related, and traffic flag-related features. Further, they applied FS to select the relevant features from each group and merge them to use during the training of their model, improving the model's performance. Similarly, Laisen Nie et al. [15] developed an MTL method using LSTM to predict the IIoT backbone network traffic accurately. Using MTL with an oversampling technique, Lijian Sun et al. [16] developed a solution to handle the data imbalance and achieve high performance in IoT networks' high-variation data sources. Their experiment is performed using the UNSW-NB15 and CICIDS-2018 datasets and shows the effectiveness of their model over the single-task learning models. Moreover, to detect network intrusions effectively, Qigang et al. [17] also developed an MTL approach that comprises a supervised learning-based clustering model, an AE-based contrastive learning model, and an MLP-based classifier. They extend their work by exploring important features for each particular task and also develop a loss function to handle the data imbalance. Their approaches show the effectiveness of MTL in network intrusion detection. Further, Huang et al. [18], [19], and Li et al. [20] also developed MTL methods to detect

intrusions and malware effectively. However, these approaches are still computationally expensive for IoT devices.

Although various methods or approaches exist, as shown in Table I, we have not found any work that leverages both MVL and MTL to build a smart attack detection and mitigation system to secure the IoT network. Moreover, many authors used non-IoT datasets to experiment with their methods or approaches, which leads to low performance and a high false alarm rate when deployed into real IoT environments. So, in this paper, we present a hybrid model that leverages both MVL and MTL to secure the IoT network.

C. Problem Statement

Let's consider the variables F , C , V , and T to represent features, class labels, views, and tasks, respectively. For the set of views $V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$, corresponding to the network traffic features, $F = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$, and class labels $C = \{c_1, c_2, c_3\}$, we develop a multiview-multitask model M , such that M computes every task, $t_i \in T$, where t_i is to perform the prediction of $c_i \in C$, with respect to the required views, $v_i \in V$. Hence, the model M is defined as $MV(F) - > T$.

III. M²VT APPROACH

We proposed a hybrid smart attack detection system to detect and classify attacks from cyber-criminals in IoT networks by utilizing MVL and MTL. The system takes the feature subsets that are highly relevant to the respective class labels as multiple views. The system learns the shared information from these multiple views to perform the respective tasks concurrently. The proposed model aims to perform three related tasks, i.e., Task 1: detecting attacks (binary classification), Task 2: classification of attack categories (multiclass classification), and Task 3: classification of attack types (also a multiclass classification). All three tasks are related to each other in terms of attack behavior and attack dimension. Moreover, the system incorporates AE to extract spatial information as well as to reduce the dimension of the input views and LSTM to extract the temporal information between the related tasks.

Definition 3.1: View: A view $v_i \in V$ can be defined as a set of optimal features used to perform a task $t_i \in T$ using a model M . The model considers different views to perform different tasks. The views are generated from the spatial domain and the temporal domain.

Definition 3.2: Task: A task $t_i \in T$ is an operation performed by a model M with a set of features $f_i \in F$ on a Dataset D . The operation may be a classification or a prediction. In our approach, tasks are one binary classification and two multiclass classifications.

Definition 3.3: Multi-Task Learning (MTL): For a given set of tasks $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$, a learning model M performs the tasks simultaneously, considering a set of n losses such that the learning operation is performed with some optimization to the losses.

There are four possible combinations of learning approaches in terms of multi-view and multi-task learning. For a set of views $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and a set of tasks $T =$

TABLE I: Comparison among existing works

Approach	Ref.	View		Task		Tested on		Dataset Type		Dataset Used		Classification Type		Performed feature selection	Handled data imbalance
		Single	Multi	Single	Multi	CPU	GPU	IoT	IIoT	Benchmark	Own Dataset	Binary	Multiclass		
ML	[21]	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			
	[22]	✓		✓		✓		✓		✓				✓	
	[23]	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓	
	[24]	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	
DL	[25]	✓		✓		✓		✓		✓		✓	✓		✓
	[26]	✓		✓		✓		✓		✓			✓	✓	✓
	[27]	✓		✓		✓		✓		✓			✓	✓	
	[28]	✓		✓		✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		
	[29]	✓		✓		✓				✓	✓	✓			
MVL	[9]		✓	✓		✓				✓		✓	✓		
	[10]		✓	✓			✓	✓		✓				✓	
	[11]		✓	✓		✓	✓			✓		✓			
MTL	[14]	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	[16]	✓			✓	✓	✓			✓		✓			✓
MVL+MTL	[30]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓		✓	✓		
	proposed	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

$\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$, we can define the four learning approaches using a learning model, say M as follows.

- 1) Single-view single-task: Here, the learning model M takes a view (v_i), which is a set of features, and performs only one task (t_i), which is a prediction. Mathematically, we can represent it as $M(v_i) \Rightarrow t_i$.
- 2) Single-view multiple-tasks: Here, the learning model M takes a view (v_i), which is a set of features, and performs multiple tasks ($t_i \in T$), which are predictions. Mathematically, we can represent it as $M(v_i) \Rightarrow T$.
- 3) Multiple-views single-task: Here, the learning model M takes multiple views ($v_i \in V$), which are multiple sets of features, and performs only one task (t_i), which is a prediction. Mathematically, we can represent it as $M(V) \Rightarrow t_i$.
- 4) Multiple-views multiple-tasks: Here, the learning model M takes multiple views ($v_i \in V$), which are multiple sets of features, and performs multiple tasks ($t_i \in T$), which are predictions. Mathematically, we can represent it as $M(V) \Rightarrow T$.

A. Multi-view learning

MVL is an emerging paradigm in ML or DL that mimics the human learning process in real-world scenarios where different perspectives or views of the data can provide supporting information during the learning process [6]. MVL leverages information from multiple views to improve the model's generalization performance. In MVL, each view represents a different perspective of data and assumes that the combination of these views can lead to a more inclusive and accurate understanding of the underlying patterns, which is required when data is heterogeneous and different views provide diverse information.

In this work, we consider different subsets of features from the available features as different views, i.e., a feature subset for performing attack detection as one view, attack types as another view, and so on. We select the respective feature subsets as views based on their relevance to the particular tasks. For example, the features that are highly relevant in

detecting an attack are considered as a view. To identify the highly relevant features, we leverage the wrapper-based FS method (forward selection) using the random forest as an estimator. This FS method selects the optimal feature subsets for each respective class label. The purpose of incorporating feature selection is to address the fact that, even when tasks or class labels are related, a subset of features that is highly relevant to one particular task may not necessarily be relevant to another related task. Since all tasks are interconnected, comprehensive information can be derived by combining the relevant subset of features for a specific task with the subsets relevant to the remaining related tasks. This combined information encompasses all necessary details for each task, making multitask learning an effective approach. We chose Random Forest (RF) as the estimator due to its ability to handle non-linear relationships, its inherent feature importance ranking, and its robustness in dealing with high-dimensional data. Random Forest effectively mitigates challenges such as the risk of overfitting and computational complexity, making it a suitable choice for feature selection in our study. Moreover, we incorporate respective AE into each view to extract spatial features and reduce the dimensions of the views. Further, these views are processed using MTL, as explained below.

In multi-view learning, the AE extracts the set of spatial features from the given input views. The spatial features are merged together in the concatenation layer using an append operation. The append operation combines all the values given as output by the ReLU activation function used in the latent layer of the AE. The values obtained from the multiple views having redundant features will not yield redundant information at the concatenation layer, as ReLU's output for the same feature presence in different views yields different information.

Mathematically, we discuss the functionality of the concatenation as follows. For a view $v_i \in V$, the output achieved from the AE is a lower-dimensional spatial feature vector (sp_i) containing spatial information of v_i . Let $Append()$ be an append function that takes all the outputs, i.e., the set of spatial feature vectors $sp_i \forall v_i \in V$, as inputs, and generates

the combined feature vector.

$$C_{vectors} = Append(sp_i) \quad (1)$$

The $C_{vectors}$ keeps the actual spatial information of the multiple views irrespective of the actual input feature space.

B. Multi-task learning

MTL learns shared information to perform multiple tasks adaptively that provide improved model generalization, which was initially introduced by Rich Caruana [31]. Moreover, it is also used in many domains of IoT, like anomaly detection, network traffic analysis, cross-domain learning, etc. In DL, MTL can be performed either by hard or soft parameter sharing of hidden layers. However, a common approach is to use a shared feature extractor and multiple heads for each specific task. The shared feature extractor is used to extract features from the input data and is shared across all the tasks. The heads for each specific task are to perform respective tasks (predictions) and are typically connected to the shared feature extractor. In our proposed model, we employed LSTM layers as the shared feature extractor to extract the temporal information and three task-specific heads to perform Task 1: attack detection, Task 2: classification of attack categories, and Task 3: classification of attack types.

In our multi-task learning, the shared layers extract the temporal features from the combined spatial information using the LSTM network with the ReLu activation function. Next, the learning operation for multiple tasks is performed at the concatenation layers of the task-specific heads. The concatenation layer takes two inputs, viz., temporal features and spatial features. Now, similar to the concatenation layer defined in the MVL block, the append operation of the concatenation layers in the MTL block is performed using equation 1. Unlike other MTL models, we don't define an aggregate optimization technique in our model. Instead, we use the Adam optimization technique as defined in equation 2 to optimize the incurred loss given by the model on each task.

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \frac{\eta}{\sqrt{\hat{v}_t + \epsilon}} \cdot \hat{m}_t \quad (2)$$

In the above equation, optimized weights at a time slot t are represented as θ_t with a learning rate η , considering a small constant defined as ϵ . This constant plays a major role in keeping the stability of the denominator. Moreover, the other two parameters, viz., \hat{v}_t and \hat{m}_t , represent the first and second momentum of the correct bias, respectively.

C. M^2VT model

The proposed hybrid model is known as M^2VT , which combines MVL and MTL to obtain a generalized model. The structure of the proposed model is illustrated in Fig. 1. The model is broadly divided into MVL and MTL blocks. In the MVL block, there are three input layers, each for respective views or tasks, followed by three respective AEs. These AEs extract spatial information as well as reduce the dimension of each input. The number of nodes or neurons of the AE layers varies and is adapted accordingly based on

the dataset and dimension of the input view. Moreover, AE layers used the 'activity_regularizer' parameter with the value 'regularizers.l1(10e-5)' and the activation function 'ReLU'. Later, these outputs of the AEs are grouped together using the 'Concatenation Layer'. Further, the output from this 'Concatenation Layer' is reshaped into the proper dimension using the 'Reshape Layer' to fit into the following 'Shared Layers' of the MTL block.

In the MTL block, the sub-block 'Shared Layers' takes the output of the MVL's 'Reshape Layer' to extract the temporal information of the input data. This sub-block contains two consecutive 'LSTM' layers, i.e., LSTM 1 and LSTM 2. These LSTM layers contain 16 units with activation function 'ReLU' and 'return_sequence' parameters as 'True'. The 'Flatten layer' takes the output of the 'LSTM 2' and converts the dimension to fit into the 'task-specific heads' sub-blocks. There are three task-specific sub-blocks to perform: Task 1, Task 2, and Task 3. The task-specific heads contain a 'Concatenation layer', some consecutive 'Dense layer' of activation function 'ReLU', and an output layer of the particular task. The 'Concatenation layer' combines the output of the 'Flatten Layer' with the output of the respective AE of the MVL block to consider both the spatial and temporal data information during the learning of the model. This data information from the output of the 'Concatenation Layer' is further learned by some consecutive 'Dense Layers'. This 'Some Dense layers' is a hyperparameter that needs to be fixed based on the dataset and task. Moreover, the output layer of each task-specific head is basically a 'Dense layer' with one node or neuron for the binary classification task with the activation function 'Sigmoid' and n number of nodes for the multi-class classification with the activation function 'Softmax'. Here, n is the number of classes in the class label of the particular task. More details of the proposed model are provided in the supplementary section.

1) *Algorithm for M^2VT approach:* The working of the M^2VT approach is illustrated in Algorithm 1, and Table II shows the meanings of the symbols used in the algorithm. This approach requires a dataset D with features $F = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$ and tasks $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$, and ensures performing multiple tasks. In step 1 of the algorithm, we have initialized the required parameters to keep the views (V), extracted spatial features from the views (V) with a lower dimension (SV), shared temporal features (Tf), and a combination of spatial views ($SV_{combine}$). In the next step, using the module $RF_{wrapper}$, we perform the wrapper-based feature selection using the RF classifier as an estimator to select the respective view v_i corresponding to the respective task $t_i \in T$ from the original features set (F) of the dataset (D). To select a relevant feature set for a view v_i , the $RF_{wrapper}$ module applies the forward selection on the original feature set F in an incremental way. In each iteration of the incremental approach, the $RF_{wrapper}$ module considers the accuracy as the estimator of the corresponding features subset given to the $RF_{wrapper}$. Now, the $RF_{wrapper}$ module picks the best subset of features that yields the maximum accuracy as the highly relevant features of the view v_i corresponding to the task t_i . This way, step 2 creates the view $v_{t_i} \in V$ of each task

Fig. 1: M²VT: the proposed model

$t_i \in T$. In step 3, we extract the spatial features sv_{t_i} from the view v_{t_i} for each task $t_i \in T$ using the *AE* module. The features extracted by the *AE* module yield lower dimensional feature space from the respective views. More specifically, the *AE* module takes each view v_{t_i} of the task $t_i \in T$ as input and extracts the spatial features of the task t_i as a latent space with a lower dimension from the respective input view v_{t_i} . Further, in step 4, the module *C* combines all the extracted spatial features $sv_{t_i} \in SV$ of the task $t_i \in T$ and stores the combined spatial features in $SV_{combine}$. Then, the *LSTM* module extracts the temporal features by taking the combined spatial features $SV_{combine}$. This way, the shared temporal information among the tasks is extracted. Finally, in step 5, to perform the task $t_i \in T$, i.e., the prediction p_{t_i} of t_i , the *Dense* module, utilizes the shared temporal features *Tf* with the respective extracted spatial features sv_{t_i} of t_i which are fed into the *Dense* module as inputs. The *Dense* module has a number of consecutive dense layers, where the number of layers and the corresponding output depend on the task t_i to be performed. In this way, the M²VT approach performs multiple tasks by utilizing multiple task-specific views.

2) *Complexity analysis*: The complexity of the M²VT approach, i.e., Algorithm 1 is as follows: For initializing the parameters, such as V , SV , $SV_{combine}$, and *Tf* in step 1, the algorithm takes $O(1)$ time. In step 2 of the algorithm, in creating v_n numbers of views, the RF classifier estimator during wrapper feature selection on f_n number of features in F takes $O(f_n(f_n + 1)/2) \times O(RF_n)$. Here, $O(RF_n)$ time is consumed to check the relevancy among the features using the RF estimator for n times. So, the total complexity of step 2 is $O(v_n) \times O(f_n(f_n + 1)/2) \times O(RF_n)$, i.e.,

TABLE II: Symbols used

Symbols	Meaning
D	a dataset
F	set of features
f_j	j th feature in F
T	set of tasks
t_i	a task in T
P	set of predictions
p_{t_i}	prediction of task t_i
V	set of views
v_{t_i}	view of task t_i
SV	set of extracted spatial features, from $v_{t_i} \in V$, with reduced dimensions
$RF_{wrapper}$	a wrapper-based feature selection module with RF as estimator that follows the forward selection approach to find the relevancy of a f_j to a task t_i
sv_{t_i}	an extracted spatial feature from v_{t_i} for t_i , with reduced dimension
Tf	shared temporal features
<i>AE</i>	Autoencoder module for extracting spatial features and dimension reduction
<i>LSTM</i>	LSTM module for extracting the temporal features
<i>C</i>	a module to combine all the $v_{t_i} \in V$
$SV_{combine}$	combination of all $v_{t_i} \in V$
<i>Dense</i>	dense module for prediction

$O(v_n \times (f_n^2 + f_n)/2 \times RF_n)$, which is equivalent to $O(f_n^2)$. Next, to extract the spatial features using *AE*, step 3 takes $O(i \times l \times h \times o)$, for the i number of inputs, l number of hidden layers, h number of neurons in each hidden layer of *AE*, and o number of outputs. So, the total complexity will be $O(v_n) \times O(i \times l \times h \times o)$, i.e., $O(v_n \times i \times l \times h \times o)$. This can be simplified as $O(x_1 \times y_1)$, where x_1 is $v_n \times i$ and y_1 is $l \times h \times o$. Similarly, to extract the shared temporal features using *LSTM* after combining the spatial features extracted by the individual *AEs*, the algorithm takes $O(i \times l \times h \times o)$ times. Therefore, the complexity of step 4 will be $O(1) + O(i \times l \times h \times o)$, i.e.,

Algorithm 1 : M²VT approach

```

Require: A Dataset  $D$  with features  $F = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$  and tasks  $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ 
Ensure: Predictions  $P = \{p_{t_1}, p_{t_2}, \dots, p_{t_i}\}$  where  $p_{t_i}$  is the predictions of  $t_i \in T$ 
1: Step 1: Initialization
2:  $V = \{\}$ 
3:  $SV = \{\}$ 
4:  $SV_{combine} = \{\}$ 
5:  $Tf = \{\}$ 
6: Step 2: Creating views
7: for  $t_i \in T$  do
8:    $v_{t_i} \leftarrow \{\}$ 
9:   for  $f_j \in F$  do
10:     $relevant \leftarrow RF_{wrapper}(f_j, v_{t_i}, t_i)$ 
11:    if  $f_j$  is relevant to  $t_i$  then
12:       $v_{t_i} \leftarrow f_j$ 
13:    end if
14:  end for
15:   $V \leftarrow v_{t_i}$ 
16: end for
17: Step 3: Spatial feature extraction and dimension reduction
18: for  $v_{t_i} \in V$  do
19:    $sv_{t_i} \leftarrow AE(v_{t_i})$ 
20:    $SV \leftarrow sv_{t_i}$ 
21: end for
22: Step 4: Temporal features extraction
23:  $SV_{combine} \leftarrow C(sv_{t_i} \in SV)$ 
24:  $Tf \leftarrow LSTM(SV_{combine})$ 
25: Step 5: Performing respective tasks (predictions)
26: for  $t_i \in T$  do
27:    $p_{t_i} \leftarrow Dense(Tf, sv_{t_i})$ 
28:    $P \leftarrow p_{t_i}$ 
29: end for

```

$O(1+i \times l \times h \times o)$. This can be simplified as $O(x_2 \times y_2)$, where x_2 is $i \times l$ and y_2 is $h \times o$. Finally, to predict the respective task as p_{t_i} corresponding to the number of $t_n \in T$ using the *Dense* module, the algorithm performs one task with a cost of $O(i \times l \times h \times o)$. Therefore, the complexity of performing t_n number of tasks in T will be $O(t_n) \times O(i \times l \times h \times o)$. This can be simplified as $O(x_3 \times y_3)$, where x_3 is $t \times i \times l$ and y_3 is $h \times o$.

So, the total complexity of our M²VT approach is $O(1) + O(f_n^2) + O(x_1 \times y_1) + O(x_2 \times y_2) + O(x_3 \times y_3)$. Taking the higher-order complexity, this can be written as $O(f_n^2)$.

IV. EVALUATION

The whole experiment is performed on a Windows 11 Pro workstation. This system has an Intel Xeon Gold 5220R processor (speed 2.2 GHz), 64GB RAM, and an NVIDIA T1000 4GB GPU card with 896 CUDA cores. We used Python (version 3.10.13) with Pandas, Numpy, Matplotlib, Scikit-learn, and Keras packages to build and analyse the proposed model. The experiment is carried out on four benchmark IoT datasets as well as on our testbed dataset.

A. Data descriptions

In this paper, we aim to build a smart attack detection system for securing IoT networks. So, we carried out experiments on a testbed IoT dataset collected by creating diverse attack scenarios with multiple IoT devices as well as on four benchmarks, publicly available IoT datasets, i.e., UNSW-BoTIoT, X-IIoTID, Edge-IIoT, and N-BaIoT. The summary of these datasets is given in Table III. Moreover, our testbed architecture is illustrated in Fig. 2. The testbed comprises seven IoT devices, two Raspberry Pi units, an intelligent

network switch, a wireless access point, multiple attacker systems, two normal user systems, a local server, and a network monitoring and traffic capturing system. The seven IoT devices are custom-built using ESP32 microcontrollers, integrating sensors, including temperature and humidity, photoresistor, ultrasonic distance measure, gas, water level, dust, and soil moisture sensors. The MQTT protocol is used for communication between the IoT devices. To simulate attacks, we employ Hping3² to generate DoS and DDoS attacks targeting IoT devices. Our monitoring system enables us to capture normal and attack traffic automatically in the presence and absence of attacks for three scenarios, namely (a) Attack targeted to IoT applications, (b) Attack targeted to virtualization layers, and (c) Attack targeted to physical infrastructures. We collected the system's performance metrics, application metrics, device status, etc. We extract nine features with two class labels, containing 2,76,867 instances in total.

B. Model training

The proposed model is trained using the selected feature subsets or views. Unlike the training of conventional DL models, training an MTL model is more tricky as there is more than one task with a respective loss function to be considered during the training. It is challenging to optimize the model weights to have minimum losses in all tasks simultaneously. To handle this, during the training of the proposed model, we used the Transfer Learning [32] concept for optimizing the weights to have a minimum loss. During the training, we first trained each AE separately using its respective feature subsets or views. We used 'Keras Turner' and trained for 50 epochs with 32 'batch_size' to achieve the optimal dimension of the encoder output.

After obtaining the favourable weights and encoder's output dimension of the AE, we change the layer parameters to be 'non-trainable', which means the weight of the layer will not be updated in further training. Since training a DL model becomes challenging to achieve higher performance if the number of classes in the class label is higher, we trained the model for 2 or 3 (the number of tasks) consecutive times, starting by focusing on the task with the highest number of classes and gradually followed by focusing on the task with the lower number of classes to achieve high performance.

C. Result analysis

The performance of M²VT is analyzed considering the commonly used evaluation measures, viz., Accuracy (AC), Precision (PR), Recall (RC), F1-score (F1), Matthew's correlation coefficient (MCC), and Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC).

1) *Comparison against the conventional DL model:* We compared the performance of the proposed M²VT model against the conventional DL model (single view - single task) based on the respective datasets. These conventional DL models are the segregated models from the proposed model. As presented in Table IV, the proposed model outperforms

²<https://www.kali.org/tools/hping3/>

TABLE III: Dataset description

Sl. No.	Datasets	Total no. of instances		Total no. of features		No. of classes		
		Original	After sampling	Original	After feature selection	Attack detection	Attack categories	Attack types
1	UNSW-BoTIoT	36,68,522	7,29,368	43	18	2	5	8
2	X-IIoTID	8,20,834	10,04,188	65	45	2	10	19
3	Edge-IIoT	19,09,671	10,19,085	63	21	2	5	15
4	N-BaIoT	70,62,606	28,79,415	115	15	2		11
5	Testbed	2,76,867	5,59,095	9	8	2	3	

Fig. 2: Testbed setup

the conventional DL models in all respective tasks on all the datasets used in this experiment. However, during the experiment, we did not include the view and the task-specific head for the Edge-IIoT dataset to perform Task 1, i.e., attack detection, as we identified in the data preprocessing part, for attack detection, either the feature ‘mqtt.conack.flags-0.0’, or ‘mqtt.protoname-0.0’, or ‘mqtt.topic-0.0’ can perfectly detect the attack (can classify the attacks from the normal) without any learning model. So, we keep the performance of both M²VT and the conventional DL model as 100% in all performance metrics for performing Task 1 of the Edge-IIoT dataset. Moreover, the ROC curve given by the M²VT in performing Task 3 of the X-IIoTID dataset is illustrated in Fig. 3. The figure represents each class’s perfect classification in Task 3 of the X-IIoTID dataset. In addition, ROC curves given by the M²VT in the other used datasets are presented in the supplementary section.

2) *Comparison against the state-of-the-art methods:* The performance of the proposed model is compared against the state-of-the-art methods based on the respective Tasks as follows:

- i) Performance comparison based on Task 1: As shown in Table V, in performing Task 1 of the UNSW-BoTIoT dataset, the M²VT outperformed the compared methods and yields a similar performance with the RF-IFPCC [34], XGB [36], SVM [38], DNN [39], RandomTree [36], and KNN-KBest [22] methods. Moreover, the PR%, RC%, and F1% values show the stability of M²VT in performing the task. Further, in performing Task 1 of the X-IIoTID dataset, the M²VT outperformed all the compared existing methods and performed similarly to PIGNUS [46]. Moreover, in the Edge-IIoT dataset, the M²VT outperformed all the compared existing methods and performed similarly to the CNN+LSTM [28] method. In addition, the M²VT gives similar performance to LSTM [52], DNN [39], RF-SMOTE [53], and LR [54] methods and outperformed the other compared methods in performing Task 1 of the N-BaIoT dataset.
- ii) Performance comparison based on Task 2: As shown in Table VI, in performing Task 2 of the UNSW-BoTIoT dataset, the M²VT outperformed the FNN and SNN

TABLE IV: Comparing M²VT with conventional DL model

Sl. no.	Datasets	Task	M ² VT					Conventional DL				
			AC%	PR%	RC%	F1%	MCC%	AC%	PR%	RC%	F1%	MCC%
1	UNSW-BoTIoT	1	99.99	99.99	99.99	99.99	99.98	97.16	97.25	97.16	97.00	86.51
		2	98.49	98.48	98.49	98.48	97.80	45.9	56.58	45.9	42.65	40.58
		3	96.74	97.31	96.74	96.72	96.21	92.17	92.78	92.17	92.14	91.15
2	X-IIoTID	1	99.88	99.88	99.88	99.88	98.85	99.85	99.85	99.85	99.85	98.53
		2	99.91	99.91	99.91	99.91	99.90	98.78	98.78	98.78	98.78	98.60
		3	99.91	99.91	99.91	99.91	99.91	99.81	99.81	99.81	99.81	99.80
3	Edge-IIoT	1	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
		2	99.15	99.15	99.15	99.15	98.94	93.09	93.13	93.09	93.02	92.61
		3	99.19	99.20	99.19	99.19	99.13	93.56	93.61	93.56	93.57	91.87
4	N-BaIoT	1	99.97	99.97	99.97	99.97	99.81	99.95	99.95	99.95	99.95	99.71
		3	88.27	83.80	88.27	85.24	87.90	85.04	81.13	85.04	81.99	84.33
5	Testbed	1	99.32	99.32	99.32	99.32	98.46	96.62	96.62	96.62	96.62	92.35
		2	98.83	98.84	98.83	98.83	98.25	98.59	98.58	98.59	98.58	97.88

TABLE VI: Comparison on Task 2

Dataset	Ref.	Method Name	AC%	PR%	RC%	F1%
UNSW-BoTIoT	[39]	DNN	99.96	99.2	99.96	99.57
	[60]	Hybrid IDS	99.97			
	[41]	FNN	95.00			
	[41]	SNN	91.00			
	Proposed	M ² VT	98.49	98.20	97.46	97.87
X-IIoTID	[43]	DT	99.49	97.33	97.20	97.27
	[43]	DNN	97.88	97.69	93.13	95.24
	[43]	GRU	99.47	97.11	96.69	96.89
	[46]	PIGNUS	97.90	88.00	95.00	88.23
	[61]	MLP - 3 - Layer	98.27	98.31	97.77	98.03
	[61]	MLP - 7 - Layer	98.10	98.07	97.56	97.80
	[62]	Residual - CNN	97.73	97.32	97.38	97.35
	[62]	Deep - CNN	96.65	96.67	97.29	96.93
	[63]	CNN - MLP	98.16	97.88	98.31	98.08
	[64]	L-CNN-MLP	98.41	97.35	98.09	97.70
Proposed	M ² VT	99.91	99.91	99.91	99.91	
Edge-IIoT	[65]	F-BIDS	90.91	92.83	93.83	93.00
	[51]	DNN	96.01	91.83	84.16	89.50
	[28]	CNN+LSTM	98.69	97.91		
	Proposed	M ² VT	99.15	99.23	99.28	99.25

TABLE V: Comparison on Task 1

Dataset	Ref.	Method Name	AC%	PR%	RC%	F1%	
UNSW-BoTIoT	[33]	LSVMS_RRBS	99.48	97.46	99.71	98.55	
	[34]	RF-IFPCC	99.99	99.99	100.0	99.99	
	[35]	ACOCN	99.96	100.0	99.96	99.98	
	[35]	LPCCN	99.97	100.0	99.97	99.98	
	[36]	XGB	99.99	99.50	97.50	98.50	
	[30]	M2VT-IDS	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	
	[37]	CNN 3D	99.90	99.75	99.85	99.80	
	[38]	SVM	99.99	99.99	100.0	86.58	
	[39]	DNN	100.0	98.56	100.0	99.27	
	[36]	RandomTree	99.99	100.0	100.0	100	
	[22]	KNN-KBest	99.99	99.00	99.00	99.00	
	[40]	RF	99.20	97.50	99.05	98.27	
	[41]	FNN	95.00	95.00	95.00	95.00	
	[42]	FNN	99.00	99.00	99.00	99.00	
	Proposed	M ² VT	99.99	99.98	99.98	99.98	
	X-IIoTID	[43]	DT	99.54	99.54	99.54	99.54
		[43]	DNN	98.96	98.97	98.94	98.95
		[43]	GRU	99.46	99.46	99.45	99.45
		[44]	CNN	99.10	99.02	99.05	99.03
[44]		LSTM	99.05	99.03	99.01	99.01	
[44]		CNN +LSTM	99.84	99.67	99.55	99.60	
[45]		RF	99.72	99.72	99.72	99.72	
[46]		PIGNUS	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	
[47]		AMPPSO+RF	98.81		98.85		
Proposed	M ² VT	99.88	99.88	99.88	99.88		
Edge-IIoT	[48]	J48	99.51	99.50	99.50	99.50	
	[48]	PART	99.55	99.50	99.50	99.50	
	[49]	RNN+LSTM	98.88	97.46	96.57	96.91	
	[50]	DT	96.00	86.00	85.00	85.00	
	[51]	DNN	99.99	99.99	99.97	99.98	
	[28]	CNN+LSTM	100.0	100.0			
Proposed	M ² VT	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0		
N-BaIoT	[52]	LSTM	99.98	100.0	99.98	99.98	
	[39]	LSVMSRRBS	99.81	99.70	99.82	99.78	
	[39]	DNN	99.99	100.0	99.98	99.98	
	[53]	RF-SMOTE	99.98	100.0	99.97	99.98	
	[54]	LR	99.98	99.90	99.96	99.92	
	[54]	ANN	96.40	93.90	95.10	99.13	
	[55]	NB-J48-ANN	99.10				
	[56]	CART	99.00				
	[57]	RNN	89.75				
	[58]	Collective DL	99.84				
	[59]	LGBA-NN	99.00				
Proposed	M ² VT	99.97	99.97	99.97	99.97		

TABLE VII: Comparison on Task 3

Dataset	Ref.	Method Name	AC%	PR%	RC%	F1%
UNSW-BoTIoT	[66]	DT	99.99			
	[66]	NB	97.50			
	[30]	M2VT-IDS	99.82	99.76	99.84	99.80
	Proposed	M ² VT	97.74	97.10	96.82	96.93
	[43]	DT	99.45	94.16	93.54	93.80
X-IIoTID	[43]	DNN	98.39	94.11	90.05	91.73
	[43]	GRU	99.46	96.47	91.58	93.54
	[44]	CNN	99.26	99.18	99.14	99.15
	[44]	LSTM	98.91	98.86	98.82	98.84
	[44]	CNN +LSTM	99.80	99.38	99.72	99.54
	[67]	CDAE-DNN	97.21			
	Proposed	M ² VT	99.91	99.91	99.91	99.91
Edge-IIoT	[68]	Inception Time	94.94	98.30	92.40	95.30
	[48]	J48	92.92	93.8	92.90	92.90
	[69]	MLP	99.98	99.95	99.98	99.96
	[65]	F-BIDS	90.93	88.06	92.20	89.00
	[51]	DNN	94.67	80.02	77.00	77.34
	Proposed	M ² VT	99.19	99.20	99.19	99.19
N-BaIoT	[70]	SNN		69.14	63.38	65.22
	Proposed	M ² VT	88.27	83.80	88.27	85.24

Fig. 3: ROC given by M^2VT on performing Task 3 of X-IloTID dataset

[41] methods. Moreover, M^2VT outperformed all the compared existing methods in performing Task 2 of the X-IloTID and Edge-IloT datasets.

- iii) Performance comparison based on Task 3: As shown in Table VII, in performing Task 3 of the UNSW-BoTIoT dataset, the M^2VT outperformed the NB [66] method. Moreover, the M^2VT outperformed the compared existing methods in performing Task 3 of X-IloTID, Edge-IloT, and N-BaloT datasets.

More detailed analyses, including performance comparisons based on ROC curves and class-wise prediction, are provided in the supplementary section.

In this study, we did not include training and testing execution times to compare the efficiency of the proposed model against existing DL-based methods. These execution times are inherently influenced by system configurations and specifications, making them biased and inconsistent across different environments. Instead, we assessed the lightness of the proposed model based on its size, specifically the number of trainable parameters, as computational costs for DL-based methods are directly tied to model size. While no existing DL-based methods in the literature are perfectly comparable to our proposed model, we compared it to some similar methods, as shown in Table VIII. The results demonstrate that the proposed model achieves a lower computational cost, performing 2 or 3 tasks simultaneously with a smaller model size, whereas the compared methods are limited to single-task performance. Additionally, Fig. 4 illustrates the impact of feature selection on model size. By using only the selected features, the proposed model is significantly smaller than when all features are used. Furthermore, as detailed in Table IX, we provide the average prediction time of the proposed model

TABLE VIII: Comparison based on the number of model sizes

Ref.	Method Name	Dataset	Classification Type	No. Of Parameters	AC%
[25]	PB-DID	UNSW-(NB15+BoTIoT)	Binary	59,530	99.00
			Multiclass (3)	59,551	96.30
[27]	CNN+LSTM	N-BaloT	Multiclass (11)	6,10,315	88.83
[26]	TCNN	UNSW-BoTIoT	Multiclass (5)	42,629	99.99
[71]	DAE	N-BaloT	Binary	36,279	
[39]	MLP	UNSW-BoTIoT	Binary	6,945	100.00
			Multiclass (5)	40,037	99.96
			Multiclass (11)	46,859	100.00
			N-BaloT	Binary	33,441
			Multiclass(10)	19,306	99.99
[9]	MS-DHRN	NSL-KDD	Binary	56,180	84.00
			Multiclass (5)		79.10
		USNW-NB15	Binary	69,670	85.70
			Multiclass (10)		76.00
CICIDS-2017	Binary	58,510	91.40		
	Multiclass (8)		90.40		
Proposed	M^2VT	UNSW-BoTIoT	Binary		99.99
			Multiclass (5)	16,196	98.49
			Multiclass (8)		97.74
			Binary		99.88
			Multiclass (10)	66,222	99.91
			Multiclass (19)		99.91
		Edge-IloT	Multiclass (6)	1,07,273	99.15
			Multiclass (15)		99.19
		N-BaloT	Binary	13,126	99.97
			Multiclass (11)		88.27
		Our Dataset	Binary	7,847	99.32
			Multiclass (3)		98.83

Fig. 4: Comparison on model size for each dataset, before and after feature selection

on both GPU and CPU systems. The experimental results indicate that the proposed model achieves faster detection times, particularly on a CPU with a clock speed of 3.5 GHz.

D. Discussion

Apart from the existing methods, which employ a common set of features to perform a single specific task, M^2VT employs multiple relevant feature subsets to perform multiple tasks concurrently, which enhances the generalization of M^2VT to yield higher performance. In this paper, M^2VT is tuned for three tasks but can be tuned for k number of tasks. Still, the model's performance will not drop because it will get more shared information during the learning. Although the proposed M^2VT model has been evaluated in offline settings, its performance has been extensively tested using five diverse benchmark IoT datasets, each collected from distinct testbed

TABLE IX: Average detection time of M²VT

Detection Time per Instance (in ms)														
Sl. No.	Datasets	GPU				CPU 2.2 GHz				CPU 3.5 GHz				
		Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	All Task at one time	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	All Task at one time	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	All Task at one time	
1	UNSW-BoTIoT	7	8	9	24	3	4	5	8	4	4	5	8	
2	X-IIoTID	13	14	15	40	7	6	8	15	5	5	7	14	
3	Edge-IIoT		14	16	33		7	8	14		6	7	12	
4	N-BaIoT	8		12	19	5	0	5	7	5		5	6	
5	Our Dataset	4	5		10	2	3		6	2	3		5	

settings and environments. The consistently high performance across these datasets demonstrates M²VT model’s strong generalization capability, highlighting its potential scalability and adaptability to real-world IoT environments. Furthermore, M²VT is designed with computational efficiency and low model complexity, making it well-suited for deployment on resource-constrained IoT devices operating in real-time network environments. Although the training of the proposed model is more challenging than the training of conventional DL, we can see the effectiveness of the M²VT, outperforming the conventional DL models with a margin of **6.17%** and the state-of-the-art methods with a margin of **1.47%**. In addition, it is also possible to improve the performance of M²VT by tuning the model’s hyperparameters. While searching for existing works to compare the proposed model’s performance, we found many methods for binary classification (*attack detection*). However, we can find only a limited number of works with little information about the details of their method, as well as their performance for the multiclass classification (classification of attack categories or classification of attack types). Although we have not yet deployed and evaluated the proposed model’s performance in a real-time or near real-time IoT environment, the prediction time of M²VT depends on the architecture, which varies according to the employed data distribution and the system’s configuration used for the model’s deployment. However, from the experiment, M²VT can separately perform only Task 1 in an average of 4 milliseconds (ms), Task 2 in an average of 4.5 ms, Task 3 in an average of 6 ms, and concurrently all three tasks in an average of 7 ms. After performing rigorous experiments on the validation of M²VT, we found the following novel points of our method.

- M²VT is a unique hybrid architecture that leverages MVL and MTL, incorporating AE and LSTM.
- It concurrently considers multiple task-specific relevant features subsets to perform multiple tasks.
- From the experimental analysis, M²VT performs better than the conventional DL methods. However, it gives higher and similar performance compared to the state-of-the-art methods.
- M²VT has lower complexity than the existing state-of-the-art methods.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Considering the wide applications given by IoT in today’s world and its vulnerabilities, this paper proposes a hybrid model called M²VT, leveraging MVL and MTL to detect and classify the attacks as well as their attack categories in an IoT network. The proposed model takes three relevant subsets of features as input views to perform three related tasks. The model used AE to extract spatial information from the input data and to reduce the dimension. Moreover, we also leverage LSTM to extract the shared temporal information among the tasks. The performance of the M²VT model is compared against the conventional DL method as well as with the state-of-the-art methods in terms of AC%, PR%, RC%, F1%, and MCC% on a testbed dataset as well as on four benchmark IoT datasets, viz., UNSW-BoTIoT, X-IIoTID, Edge-IIoT, and N-BaIoT. From the experimental analysis, we can observe that M²VT outperformed the conventional DL models with a margin of 6.17% AC, 5.18% PR, 6.02% RC, 6.33% F1, and 7.38% MCC, as well as the state-of-the-art methods with a margin of 1.45% AC, 3.00% PR, 4.4% RC, and 3.59% F1. In the future, by deploying the M²VT model for detecting and classifying attacks, we will extend the work to prevent cyber-attacks in an IoT environment, which is not included in this work. Moreover, we will perform more experiments to improve the proposed model’s performance and to evaluate the robustness of the model, such as by tuning the model’s hyperparameters or incorporating other DL architectures like CNN and using more IoT benchmark datasets.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Due to page limitations, we have included additional details, results, and analyses of our approach in the following sections.

A. Comparison with existing works

Here we provide an additional comparison among existing works with the proposed M²VT approach in Table A10 to highlight the difference between our experiment and existing works.

B. Threat model

This work considers a threat model in which adversaries may originate from both internal and external sources and are capable of launching a wide-range of cyber-attacks, including DoS, DDoS, MiTM, Scan, Spyware, Ransomware, Bruteforce, etc. These attacks target the confidentiality, availability, and

integrity of the IoT system. We assume that the adversaries do not possess the knowledge of the internal architecture of the M²VT model but do have access to the IoT network and can execute various attacks. The M²VT model is designed to detect these cyber-attacks in real-time with high accuracy and minimal cost.

C. Proposed Model's Description

The detailed description of the proposed M²VT model, including the layer types, number of nodes, output shapes, used activation functions, the layers connected to, and hyperparameters for each respective dataset and task-specific heads used in this experiment, is given in Table A11. The proposed model is compiled with the 'Adam' optimizer with its default learning rate and loss function 'binary_crossentropy' for the binary classification task and 'sparse_categorical_crossentropy' for the multi-class classification tasks.

TABLE A10: Comparison among prior works

Ref.	Based On	Method Name	Dataset	Classification Type	Performance (AC%)
[21]	ML (GB, DT)		NLS-KDD IoT-23 UNSW-BotIoT Edge-IIoT	Binary	99.81 99.98 100.0 100.0
[22]	ML	kNN	UNSW-BoTIoT		99.99
[33]	ML(SVM)	LSVM	KDD99 UNSW-BoTIoT N-BaIoT	Binary	95.66 99.48 99.81
[23]	ML(Ensemble)	ELBA-IoT	N-BaIoT	Binary & Multiclass(3)/(10)	100.0/100.0/99.6
[24]	ML	IDS-SIoEL	IoT-23 UNSW-BoTIoT Edge-IIoT	Binary	99.98 99.99 100.0
[53]	ML(RF)	RF-SMOTE	NSL-KDD N-BaIoT	Binary	98.31 99.98
[72]	ML	DT	X-IIoTID	Binary	99.58
[25]	DL (LSTM)	PB-DID	UNSW (NB15 + BoTIoT)	Binary & Multiclass(3)	99.00 / 96.30
[26]	DL(CNN)	TCNN	UNSW-BoTIoT	Multiclass (5)	99.99
[27]	DL (Hybrid)	CNN+ LSTM	N-BaIoT	Multiclass(11)	88.83
[28]	DL (Hybrid)	CNN+ LSTM	Edge-IIoT	Binary & Multiclass(6)	100.0/98.96
[44]	DL(Hybrid)	CNN+ LSTM	UNSW-NB15 X-IIoTID	Binary & Multiclass(10) Binary & Multiclass(19)	93.21/92.90 99.84/98.80
[46]	DL(Hybrid)	PIGNUS	Gas Pipeline Water-Storage Tank NSL-KDD UNSW-NB15 X-IIoTID	Binary & Multiclass	100.0/97.83 average
[9]	MVL	MS-DHRN	NSL-KDD USNW-NB15 CICIDS-2017	Binary & Multiclass(5) Binary & Multiclass(10) Binary & Multiclass(8)	84.00/79.10 85.70/76.0 91.40/90.40
[10]	MVL + FL	MV-FLD	MQTTset	Binary	94.17
[11]	MVL		Drebin AMD	Binary	91.00 DR 81.00 DR
[14]	MTL(LSTM)		simulation	Binary & Multiclass	92.63/88.45
[16]	MTL		UNSB-NB18 CICIDS-2018	Binary	90% average DR
Proposed	Hybrid (MVL + MTL)	M ² VT	UNSW-BotIoT X-IIoTID Edge-IIoT N-BaIoT Own Dataset	Binary & Multiclass(5)/(8) Binary & Multiclass(10)/(19) Binary & Multiclass(5)(15) Binary & Multiclass(11) Binary & Multiclass(3)	99.99/98.49/96.74 99.88/99.91/99.91 100.0/99.15/99.19 99.97/88.27 99.32/98.83

TABLE A11: Models’ description for the respective datasets

Sl. no.	Dataset	Models’ description																								Total model parameters							
		Input						Encode						Combine						Shared information							Task heads						Output
Layer no. (L)	Layer type	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	Dense	Sigmoid	Softmax					
Activation function	Layer no. (L)	Dense						Concatenate						LSTM						Concatenate						Dense						Dense	
Layer no. (L)	Layer type	Relu						Relu						Relu						Relu						Relu						Dense	
1	UNSW-BoTIoT	(, 4)	(, 6)	(, 7)	(, 3)	(, 5)	(, 6)	(, 14)	(, 14, 1)	(, 14, 16)	(, 14, 16)	(, 224)	(, 227)	(, 229)	(, 230)	(, 16)	(, 32)	(, 4)	(, 8)	(, 16)	(, 1)	(, 1)	(, 5)	(, 8)									
	Layer Connected To	L.1	L.2	L.3	L.4, 5, & 6	L.7	L.8	L.9	L.11 & 4	L.11 & 5	L.11 & 6	L.13	L.14	L.15	L.16																		
2	X-IIoT	(, 15)	(, 13)	(, 17)	(, 12)	(, 10)	(, 14)	(, 36)	(, 36, 1)	(, 36, 16)	(, 576)	(, 588)	(, 586)	(, 590)	(, 32)	(, 64)	(, 4)	(, 16)	(, 32)	(, 1)	(, 1)	(, 10)	(, 19)										
	Layer connected to	L.1	L.2	L.3	L.4, 5, & 6	L.7	L.8	L.9	L.11 & 4	L.11 & 5	L.11 & 6	L.13	L.14	L.15	L.16																		
3	Edge-IIoT	(, 12)	(, 14)			(, 10)	(, 12)	(, 22)	(, 22, 1)	(, 22, 16)	(, 352)	(, 362)	(, 364)	(, 364)	(, 128)	(, 64)	(, 64)	(, 8)	(, 32)	(, 5)	(, 5)	(, 5)	(, 15)										
	Layer connected to					L.2	L.3	L.5, & 6	L.7	L.8	L.9	L.10	L.11 & 5	L.14	L.15	L.16	L.17	L.18	L.19	L.20													
4	N-BaIoT	(, 6)		(, 8)	(, 5)		(, 7)	(, 12)	(, 12, 1)	(, 12, 16)	(, 192)	(, 197)		(, 199)	(, 32)	(, 32)	(, 8)	(, 16)			(, 1)	(, 1)	(, 11)										
	Layer connected to			L.1		L.3	L.4, & 6	L.7	L.8	L.9	L.10	L.11 & 4	L.11 & 6	L.14	L.15	L.16	L.17	L.18															
5	Testbed	(, 8)	(, 7)			(, 7)	(, 6)	(, 13)	(, 13, 1)	(, 13, 16)	(, 208)	(, 215)	(, 214)		(, 4)	(, 16)	(, 8)				(, 1)	(, 3)	(, 3)										
	Layer connected to			L.1	L.2		L.2	L.4, & 5	L.7	L.8	L.9	L.10	L.11 & 4	L.11 & 5	L.12	L.13	L.16	L.17	L.18	L.19	L.20												

D. Model Training

The detailed procedure for training the M²VT model is provided in this section. We initiate the training of the model by focusing on Task 3 (Classification of attack types) to obtain the minimal loss. The whole model is trained for 100 ‘epochs’ with 64 ‘batch_size’ with the ‘Early_Stopping’ and ‘Modelcheckpoint’ ‘callback’ options. Using the ‘callback’ options, the model is trained by monitoring Task 3’s validation loss. To speed up the training process, we put the ‘restore_best_weight’ as ‘True’ and the ‘patience’ as 10. After this, the parameters of the ‘shared layers’ and layers in Task 3’s specific head are changed to non-trainable. Again, focusing on Task 2 (Classification of attack categories), the model is retrained for the same ‘epochs’, ‘batch_size’, and ‘callback’ as before. Like before, the layer’s parameters of Task 2’s specific head are changed to non-trainable. Lastly, the model is retrained by focusing on Task 1 (Attack detection) for the same ‘epochs’, ‘batch_size’, and callback option. This way, the M²VT model is trained for each respective dataset to obtain the optimal weights to give high performance with minimum losses in all tasks simultaneously. By training the model in such a way, as in Figs. A5 and A6, we can see the gradual decreases in the model’s training and validation losses for the UNSW-BoTIoT and X-IIoT datasets. Moreover, as in Figs. A7, A8, and A9, we can see the same for Edge-IIoT, N-BaIoT, and testbed dataset. As we mentioned before, Task 1 of Edge-IIoT can be performed without any learning model, and when included, the overall performance of the proposed model is degraded. So, we choose to perform only the two tasks (i.e., tasks 3 and 2) for the Edge-IIoT dataset. Moreover, as no class label is available in the N-BaIoT dataset as well as in the testbed dataset to perform tasks 2 and 3, we performed only tasks 3 and 1 for the N-BaIoT dataset, and tasks 2 and 1 for the testbed dataset.

E. Dataset Description

The datasets used in this experiment are summarized as follows.

1) *UNSW-BoTIoT*: Cyber Range Lab (UNSW, Canberra) published this dataset for the purpose of detecting and identifying botnet traffic on IoT-specific networks³. They designed a realistic IoT environment to generate this dataset. The environment consists of network services as well as platforms, which include both legitimate and malicious virtual machines. Moreover, a simulated IoT-based smart home that includes simulated IoT devices like smart lights, garage doors, refrigerators, thermostats, and weather monitoring systems is created using the Node-Red tool to generate the IoT network traffic. They analyzed the network traffic and created the dataset using ArgusTool. The network protocols used in this environment are UDP, TCP, ICMP, IGMP, ARP, and RARP. The dataset includes both botnet and normal IoT network traffic. Botnet-based attacks like keylogging, service and OS scans, data exfiltration, and DoS and DDoS attacks (along with their types) are included in this dataset. In the dataset repository, it is

³<https://iee-dataport.org/documents/bot-iiot-dataset> available in PCAP, Argus, and CSV file formats. Moreover, the files were separated based on the label of each attack category and subcategory. The PCAP files have more than 7,20,00,000 instances of 69.3 GB in memory size, and the CSV format is the extracted flow traffic, which is 16.7 GB in memory size. In this work, we employed the full CSV format dataset available in the repository.

2) *X-IIoTID*: It is a publicly available benchmark dataset for evaluating and developing IDS/IPS, especially for IoT and IIoT [43]. The dataset was generated by simulating the techniques as well as the procedures of cyber-attackers and recording the activities of IIoT systems. The dataset contains the behaviours of new IIoT protocols, activities of devices, various attack protocols, and diverse attack types, as well as diverse scenarios. The dataset is generated from an architecture that consists of 3 levels, i.e., the edge, the platform, and the enterprise. These levels include various industrial and IoT devices, protocols (Modbus, WebSocket, MQTT, TCP, CoAP, SMTP), services, and attack systems. Moreover, it includes the network traffic of the 9 attack stages, i.e., Reconnaissance, weaponization, exploitation, lateral Movement, C&C, exfiltration, tampering, crypto-ransomware, and Ransom DoS. The dataset has 65 features from the network traffic, stats of the device's resources, and alerts or logs from various devices and links. The dataset is publicly available in CSV format with 820,830 records, where 421,417 are normal and 399,417 are malicious. Moreover, the dataset contains 18 types of attack, viz., insider malicious, reverse shell, dictionary, brute force, fuzzing, discovering resources, generic scanning, vulnerability scanning, ransomware, exfiltration, TCP relay, MQTT, MiTM, Modbus register, command control, RDoS, false data injection, and fake notification, which are generated by using CKC, MALC, and ATT&CK frameworks.

3) *Edge-IIoT*: It is another realistic cyber-security dataset of IoT and IIoT, which was used in both centralized and federated learning [51]. The dataset is generated from a realistic IoT/IIoT testbed that includes more than 10 types of IoT sensor devices, such as temperature and humidity sensors, moisture sensors, ultrasonic sensors, heart rate sensors, flame sensors, water level detection sensors, etc. The testbed is organised into 7 layers, including the perception layer, edge computing layer, software-defined networking layer, fog computing layer, blockchain network layer, Network functions virtualization layer, and cloud computing layer. The dataset is created using stats of various alerts, system resources, logs, and network traffic of each layer. It includes 14 types of IoT and IIoT-based cyber-attacks, which are further categorized into 5 attack categories, i.e., information gathering, MiTM attacks, injection attacks, malware attacks, and DoS/DDoS attacks. We leverage this dataset, specially crafted for DL models that contain 61 features and 2 class labels, i.e., 'Attack_label' for attack detection and 'Attack_type' to classify attack types. Moreover, by taking the reference to the original work, we include a class label that categorises the attack types into 5 attack categories.

4) *N-BaIoT*: It is a widely used benchmark dataset for IoT network applications and cyber-security research to defend against botnet-based IoT attacks [71]. The data are gathered from a real-time IoT environment that includes 9 IoT devices

(thermostats, doorbells, security cameras, baby monitors, and a webcam). In addition to these devices, the testbed includes an access point, a sniffer host, and a C&C server. The dataset contains both malicious and normal IoT network traffic. The malicious traffic is generated by launching 10 types of IoT-based attacks using the botnets 'Mirai' and 'BASH-LITE' (or 'Gafgyt'). The dataset is generated by considering the network packets over several temporal windows and extracting statistical features that represent the characteristics of the network. We utilized this dataset obtained from Kaggle, which is available in CSV format. The dataset includes 115 features and one class label ('label') with 10 classes. To perform 'attack detection', we append another class label where all the attack types are treated as 1 and the normal/benign as 0.

F. Data preprocessing

Data preprocessing is a crucial step in handling various issues in data, the performance of the model depends highly on it, and to obtain a generalized model. We employed the common 'Mean-Mode' based imputation methods (Mean for numerical columns and for categorical columns) to handle the missing values, and we also dropped the columns having NaN or NA values.

To convert categorical values to numerical values, we used both label encoding and one-hot encoding schemes. During the experiment, considering the computational cost and performance of the model, we prefer to use the label encoding scheme as it does not add an extra dimension to the original dataset distribution. In this experiment, using one-hot encoding over label encoding doesn't affect the performance of the model significantly, but highly on computational cost. However, in the case of the Edge-IIoT dataset, we observed that using one-hot encoding can achieve higher performance. We also find that the values of the generated feature, i.e., 'mqtt.conack.flags-0.0' or 'mqtt.protoname-0.0' or 'mqtt.topic-0.0', after applying one-hot encoding to the feature 'mqtt.conack.flags', 'mqtt.protoname', and 'mqtt.topic' is exactly matched with the values of the class label 'Attack_label' for attack detection, which means that without any learning model, by one of these features itself can differentiate an attack from the normal perfectly.

After converting the categorical values to numerical, we used the MinMaxScaler to normalize the values of the data in the range of 0 to 1. The datasets used in this experiment are highly imbalanced, i.e., there is a high variation in the number of instances between the classes. The data imbalance problem may lead to over-fitting and under-fitting scenarios that negatively affect the model's performance. To handle this issue, we used the oversampling technique 'SMOTE' to synthesise more instances for the minority classes and the undersampling technique 'RandomUnderSampler' to reduce the instances of the majority classes. We used both sampling techniques to balance the dataset and avoid increasing the number of training instances so that our system could handle the computation during the model training. To perform three tasks, the datasets we have used in this experiment have three class labels, so sampling to balance the dataset across

Fig. A5: M^2VT training vs. validation loss on UNSW-BoTIoT dataset

all three class labels is not possible. Moreover, Keras’s fit module is not yet supported to initialize weights for respective classes to balance the weightage between the classes during the training of an MTL model. Generally, as the number of classes increases in a classification problem, it becomes more challenging to build a high-performance model. So, in this work, we sampled and balanced the data distribution based on the class label with the highest number of classes. Table III also reflected the changes between the sampled data distribution over the original data distribution of respective datasets. Moreover, using the wrapper-based FS method, we select the feature subsets that are most relevant to the respective class labels. The total number and the name of the selected features for each dataset, according to the respective class labels, are given in Table A12. We considered these selected features as the views for building and evaluating the proposed model. Then, we used the ‘train_test’ split module from the Scikit-learn package to split the dataset into 80% training and 20% testing sets.

G. Segregation of M^2VT model to conventional DL models

For a better understanding of the working principles of conventional DL models used for the comparison with M^2VT , we illustrate the model segregation diagram of conventional DL models from the M^2VT in Fig. A10. The M^2VT model that takes three views to perform three respective tasks is segregated into three DL models that take a single view to perform a single respective task.

H. Experimental Results

We compared the performance of the M^2VT model against the conventional DL model in terms of Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves for each task of the respective datasets. In performing Task 1, as illustrated in Figs. A11a, A11b, A11c, and A11d for UNSW-BoTIoT, X-IIoTID, N-BaIoT and testbed dataset, the proposed model (M^2VT)

performs better than the conventional DL. Moreover, Figs. A12a and A12b show the one-vs-all ROC curves given by M^2VT and conventional DL model in classifying the classes of performing Task 2 on UNSW-BoTIoT dataset. Similarly, Figs. A13a and A13b illustrated the one-vs-all ROC curves given by M^2VT and conventional DL model in performing Task 3 on UNSW-BoTIoT dataset. These Figs. A12 and A13 show the dominance of M^2VT against the conventional DL model in performing tasks 2 and 3 on the UNSW-BoTIoT dataset. Figs. A14a and A14b illustrated the one-vs-rest ROC curves given by M^2VT and conventional DL model in classifying the classes in performing Task 2 on X-IIoTID dataset. Similarly, Figs. A15a and A15b illustrated the one-vs-rest ROC curves given by M^2VT and conventional DL model in classifying the classes in performing Task 3 on the X-IIoTID dataset. From these Figs. A14 and A15, we can observe the dominance of M^2VT against the conventional DL on the X-IIoTID dataset. Figs. A16a and A16b illustrated the one-vs-rest ROC curves given by M^2VT and conventional DL model in classifying the classes in performing Task 2 on the Edge-IIoT dataset. Similarly, Figs. A17a and A17b illustrated the one-vs-rest ROC curves given by the M^2VT and conventional DL model in classifying the classes in performing Task 3 on the Edge-IIoT dataset. From these Figs. A16 and A17, we can observe the dominance of M^2VT against the conventional DL on the Edge-IIoT dataset. Moreover, Figs. A18a and A18b illustrated the one-vs-rest ROC curves given by the M^2VT and conventional DL model in classifying the classes in performing Task 3 on the N-BaIoT dataset. Similarly, Figs. A19a and A19b illustrated the one-vs-rest ROC curves given by M^2VT and conventional DL model in classifying the classes in performing Task 2 on our own dataset. These Figs. A18 and A19 show the dominance of M^2VT against the conventional DL on the N-BaIoT dataset as well as on our testbed dataset. The curves in Figs. A11c, A14a, and A15a are overlap with one another as the M^2VT can predict each classes similarly to one another.

TABLE A12: Selected features for performing each task of the respective datasets

Dataset	UNSW-BoT/IoT			X-IIoT/ID			Edge-IIoT			N-BaIoT			Testbed dataset	
Task	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	3	1	2	
F1	Tap_P_Proto_SrcIP	AR_P_Proto_SrcIP	AR_P_Proto_SrcIP	Des_port	Des_port	Des_port	mqtc,connack flags=0/0 or mqtc, protomame- 0/0 or mqtc,logic- 0/0	tcpack_raw	tcpack_raw	tcpack_raw	H_L1_01_weight	ML_dir_L10_01_mean	mem_percent	mem_percent
F2	AR_P_Proto_DstIP	Tap_P_Proto_DstIP	Tap_P_Proto_DstIP	Des_pkts_ratio	Duration	Des_port	http.request. version=0/0	http.request. version=0/0	http.request. version=0/0	H_L1_001_variance	H_L1_01_weight	[NET]RXKBToI	[NET]RXKBToI	
F3	Tap_P_Proto	Tap_P_Proto	Tap_P_Proto	Sec_port	Sec_IP_bytes	Std_num_procs	tcp.connection. syn	tcp.connection. syn	icmp.seq_le	HH_dir_L10_1_mean	ML_dir_L10_1_weight	[NET]RXKBToI	[NET]RXKBToI	
F4	Tap_P_Proto	Tap_P_Proto	Tap_P_Proto	Des_port	Sec_IP	Sec_IP	tcp.connection. rst	udp.stream	udp.stream	HH_L5_weight	H_L1_weight	[NET]RXKBToI	[NET]RXKBToI	
F5	sbytes	Tap_P_Proto	Tap_P_Proto	Avg_num_procs	Std_num_procs	Duration	http.referrer=0/0	dis.qry.name.len=0/0	dis.qry.name.len=0/0	HH_L1_mean	HH_dir_L10_01_mean	cpu.system	cpu.system	
F6	pkts	proto	proto	Std_num_procs	Sec_port	Avg_system_time	icmp.seq_le	http.referrer=0/0	http.referrer=0/0	HH_L5_std	ML_dir_L10_01_variance	[NET]RXKBToI	cpu_idle	
F7		state	Des_IP	Des_IP	Avg_num_procs	Des_pkts_ratio	udp.stream	tcp.connection. syn	tcp.connection. syn	HH_L1_variance	HH_dir_L10_01_variance	cpu.user	cpu_idle	
F8		is_privileged	Des_IP	Des_IP	Std_lowat_time		tcp.len	tcp.connection. rst	tcp.connection. rst	HH_L1_magnitude	HH_dir_L10_01_magnitude	cpu.user	cpu_idle	
F9		read_write_physical.process	anomaly_alert	Sec_port	Sec_port		tcp.ack	tcp.len	tcp.len	HH_L10_01_indus				
F10		Service	is_SYN_ACK	is_SYN_ACK	Avg_num_procs		tcp.seq	tcp.ack	tcp.ack	H_L3_mean				
F11		Avg_system_time	Avg_system_time	Avg_system_time	Avg_kmemused		mqtc,protomame-0	tcp.seq	tcp.seq					
F12		Des_pkts	Des_pkts	Des_pkts	read_write_physical.process		tcp.flags	tcp.flags	tcp.flags					
F13		OSSEC_alert_level	is_SYN_with_RST	is_SYN_with_RST	File_activity		http.request. version=HTTP/1.1	tcp.checksum	tcp.checksum					
F14		Avg_nice_time	is_pure_ack	is_pure_ack	tcp.connection. synack		http.request. version=HTTP/1.1	http.request. version=HTTP/1.1	http.request. version=HTTP/1.1					
F15		Successful_login	Des_IP	Des_IP			http.response	http.response	http.response					
F16		Des_bytes_ratio	Des_bytes_ratio	Des_bytes_ratio	mqtc,connack flags=0x00000000		mqtc,connack flags=1471198	mqtc,connack flags=1471198	mqtc,connack flags=1471198					
F17		Comm_state	Comm_state	Comm_state			http.referrer=0	http.referrer=0	http.referrer=0					
No. Of Selected Features	4	6	7	15	13	17	1	16	17	6	10	8	7	

Selected features for performing the respective tasks

Fig. A6: M²VT training vs. validation loss on X-IIoTID dataset

Fig. A7: M²VT training vs. validation loss on Edge-IIoT dataset

Moreover, as in Fig. A15, the ROC curves given by M²VT and conventional DL are similar to one another as the two models can similarly perform Task 3 (classification of attack types) on the X-IIoTID dataset.

I. Ablation study

To evaluate and assess the impact of each component in M²VT model, we carried out an ablation study by designing six scenarios as follows.

- 1) Multi-views Multi-tasks (MVMT): This is the original M²VT model, which integrates multiple views to perform multiple tasks, incorporating Autoencoder (AE) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks.
- 2) Single-view Single-task (SVST): A conventional deep learning model that uses a single view to perform a single

task, with AE and LSTM. The selected view consists of features relevant to the specific task.

- 3) Single-view Multi-tasks (SVMT): A multitask learning (MTL) scenario using a single view derived by combining feature sets relevant to multiple tasks. AE and LSTM are included.
- 4) Multi-views Single-task (MVST): A multiview learning (MVL) scenario that uses multiple feature subsets (views) to perform a single task at a time, incorporating AE and LSTM.
- 5) Multi-views Multi-task without AE (MVMT-AE): This configuration is similar to MVMT but excludes the AE component.
- 6) Multi-views Multi-task without LSTM (MVMT-LSTM): This variant mirrors MVMT but excludes the LSTM component.

Fig. A9: M^2VT training vs. validation loss on Testbed dataset

We carried out the ablation study on each of the datasets used in this work. For the SVMT scenario, a single view was constructed by merging the respective views of all tasks, and multitask learning was performed using this combined view. In the MVST scenario, the feature subsets relevant to each task were used as multiple views, and single-task learning was performed for each task. As shown in Table A21, the proposed hybrid M^2VT model achieved the highest performance, reaching 99.99% accuracy on the UNSW-BoTIoT dataset - outperforming all other configurations, including MVL, MTL, MVMT without AE, and LSTM. Similar trends were observed across the remaining datasets, highlighting the positive and synergistic impact of each component within the proposed M^2VT architecture.

Further, we present a class-wise comparison with the existing methods based on RC% for 5-class classification of the UNSW-BoTIoT dataset in Table A13. The comparison is performed on the existing methods, which are based on both the full and the 5% of the UNSW-BoTIoT dataset. The performance of these methods highly depends on the dataset they used during their experiment. However, we found only a few works that properly mentioned the type of dataset they used in their experiment. In the literature, we have not found any information regarding the class-wise performance for the 8-class classification of the UNSW-BoTIoT dataset. So, as shown in Fig. A20, we give the M^2VT model's class-wise performance on 8-class classification as a future reference to the readers. Moreover, we perform class-wise performance

Fig. A10: Segregation of M^2VT model to conventional DL models for each respective task

comparison of the M^2VT model against the existing methods for tasks 2 and 3 of the X-IIoTID dataset based on RC% in Tables A15 and A17. Overall, the proposed model performs better than the compared methods. In addition, we also present the class-wise performance of the proposed model against the existing methods based on tasks 2 and 3 in terms of PR%, RC%, and F1%, in Table A18 and A16 for the Edge-IIoT dataset. Overall, the proposed model performs better than the compared existing methods.

In the literature, we have not found any work to compare

the performance of the M^2VT model based on Task 3 (Classification of Attack Types) of the N-BaIoT dataset in terms of AC% and overall PR%, RC%, and F1%. However, we present the class-wise performance comparison against the existing methods in Table A19. The M^2VT model performs similarly to the DNN [53] methods and better than the SNN [70] method. Moreover, as shown in Table A14, M^2VT model yields higher performance in class-wise comparison with the conventional DL model.

Fig. A11: Comparison of M^2VT with conventional DL when performing Task 1

TABLE A13: Class-wise comparison based on RC% in 5-class classification on UNSW-BoTloT dataset

Ref.	Method Name	DDoS	DoS	Normal	Recon	Theft
[60]	IF- CSVM	99.38	99.53	88.91	44.76	99.32
[73]	LAE-BLSTM	98.96	98.95	91.89	99.95	96.68
[74]	ANN XGB	97.26	99.35	100.0	99.93	100.0
[39]	DNN	99.85	99.83	100.0	99.93	100.0
[75]	AILBSM	98.50	98.70	88.70	98.70	83.53
Proposed	M^2VT	94.50	93.24	99.91	99.61	100.0

Fig. A12: Comparison of M²VT with conventional DL when performing Task 2 using UNSW-BoTIoT dataset

Fig. A13: Comparison of M²VT with conventional DL when performing Task 3 using the UNSW-BoTIoT dataset

TABLE A14: Class-wise performance comparison on 3-class classification on testbed dataset

Method	Performance Metrics	DoS	DDoS	Normal
Conventional DL	PR%	98.25	99.26	98.24
	RC%	97.62	99.85	98.27
	F1%	97.94	99.55	98.26
M ² VT	PR%	99.26	98.19	99.07
	RC%	97.31	100	99.17
	F1%	98.27	99.09	99.12

Fig. A15: Comparison of M²VT with conventional DL when performing Task 3 using X-IIoTID dataset

TABLE A15: Comparison based on RC% of 9-class classification on X-IIoTID dataset

Ref.	Method Name	C&C	Crypto_ransom	Exfiltrate	Exploit	Lateral Movement	RDOS	Recon	Tamper	Weaponize
[43]	DT	89.66	99.86	89.76	98.52	99.48	99.99	99.22	99.47	99.97
[43]	DNN	77.16	81.88	99.91	81.29	97.69	99.96	95.85	98.15	99.94
[43]	GRU	88.26	96.94	99.93	86.23	97.89	99.98	98.86	99.18	99.97
[46]	PIGNUS	68.00	99.00	100.0	98.00	100.0	100.0	100.0	96.00	94.00
[64]	L-CNN-MLP	98.34	99.65	100.0	99.44	98.27	99.75	95.41	98.35	99.41
Proposed	M ² VT	100.0	100.0	99.97	100.0	99.96	100.0	99.95	99.99	99.99

TABLE A16: Class-wise performance comparison on 15-class classification on the Edge-IIoT dataset

Class	PR%					RC%					F1%				
	[48] J48	[69] MLP	[65] F-BIDS	[51] DNN	Proposed M ² VT	[48] J48	[69] MLP	[65] F-BIDS	[51] DNN	Proposed M ² VT	[48] J48	[69] MLP	[65] F-BIDS	[51] DNN	Proposed M ² VT
Backdoor	99.90	96.00	95.00	95.00	99.97	93.20	98.00	99.00	86.00	99.75	96.50	97.00	97.00	90.00	99.86
HTTP	75.40	96.00	82.00	76.00	99.60	92.60	97.00	56.00	92.00	98.10	83.10	96.00	65.00	83.00	98.84
ICMP	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.91	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.00	99.99	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.95
TCP	100.0	100.0	100.0	82.00	99.18	100.0	100.0	93.00	100.0	98.14	100.0	100.0	96.00	90.00	98.65
UDP	99.90	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.90	99.90	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.95
F_print	59.30	98.00	64.00	59.00	99.63	80.40	94.00	100.0	64.00	99.45	88.90	96.00	78.00	61.00	99.54
MfTM	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	52.90	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	69.20	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Normal	98.30		100.0	100.0	100.0	98.90		100.0	100.0	100.0	98.60		100.0	100.0	100.0
Password	98.50	100.0	63.00	55.00	96.20	74.30	100.0	76.00	38.00	95.19	84.70	100.0	66.00	45.00	95.69
Port_scan	92.30	99.00	95.00	100.0	98.21	96.70	97.00	95.00	50.00	99.49	94.40	98.00	95.00	66.00	98.85
Ransome	82.10	99.00	97.00	73.00	99.96	95.80	96.00	97.00	85.00	99.75	88.40	96.00	97.00	79.00	99.85
Injection	75.30	100.0	67.00	47.00	96.33	90.90	100.0	81.00	71.00	98.11	82.40	100.0	72.00	57.00	97.21
Upload	99.30	100.0	63.00	67.00	98.33	84.50	100.0	91.0	48.00	96.68	91.30	100.0	74.00	56.00	97.50
vul_scan	92.92	100.0	96.00	96.00	99.47	96.60	100.0	99.00	85.00	99.37	96.60	100.0	97.00	90.00	99.42
XSS	93.00	97.00	99.00	53.00	98.13	78.00	93.00	96.00	37.00	99.29	84.90	95.00	98.00	43.00	98.71

TABLE A17: Comparison based on RC% of 18-class classification on X-IIoTID dataset

Classes	Ref. & Method Name				
	[43] DT	[43] DNN	[43] GRU	[44] CNN+ LSTM	Proposed (M ² VT)
Brute Force	99.98	99.94	99.99	99.86	100.0
C&C	86.62	84.81	89.03	99.82	100.0
Crypto_ransom	97.38	94.76	93.89	99.82	100.0
Dictionary	95.41	99.57	99.65	99.81	100.0
Exfiltrate	99.61	99.91	99.92	99.76	100.0
Generic_Scan	99.86	99.72	99.39	99.85	99.88
Vul_Scan	85.71	99.82	99.82	99.76	99.85
RDOS	76.77	99.95	99.96	99.87	99.99
False_data_injection	99.95	98.43	98.68	99.88	99.91
Discovering_resources	99.84	83.22	95.52	99.86	99.99
Reverse_shell	67.52	87.80	89.47	99.79	99.98
MiTM	99.83	45.30	45.30	99.87	100.0
TCP replay	99.44	70.46	72.30	99.82	99.91
Fake notification	99.89	82.14	82.14	99.78	100.0
Fuzzing	99.99	67.56	75.78	99.84	100.0
insider_malicious	90.16	99.96	99.83	99.82	100.0
Modbus_register_reading	79.94	99.76	99.80	99.85	100.0
MQTT_cloud_broker_subscription	99.80	99.54	99.78	99.81	99.97

TABLE A18: Class-wise performance comparison on 6-class classification on Edge-IIoT dataset

Ref.	Method Name	Performance Metrics	Dos_DDoS	MiTM	Scan	Injection	Malware	Normal
[65]	F-BIDS	PR%	94.00	100.0	93.00	86.00	84.00	100.0
		RC%	89.00	100.0	96.00	83.00	95.00	100.0
		F1%	91.00	100.0	95.00	84.00	88.00	100.0
[51]	DNN	PR%	92.00	100.0	96.00	66.00	97.00	100.0
		RC%	99.00	94.00	74.00	90.00	48.00	100.0
		F1%	95.00	97.00	84.00	97.00	64.00	100.0
[28]	CNN+LSTM	PR%	91.00	100.0	94.00	68.00	95.00	100.0
Proposed	M ² VT	PR%	99.85	100.0	99.17	97.10	99.27	100.0
		RC%	99.20	100.0	99.67	98.89	97.92	100.0
		F1%	99.52	100.0	99.42	97.98	98.59	100.0

TABLE A19: Class-wise performance comparison on multiclass classification on the N-BaIoT dataset

Performance Metrics	Ref.	Method Name	Benign	Combo	Junk	gScan	TCP	gUDP	Ack	mScan	Syn	mUDP	UDPP
PR%	[53]	DNN	99.94	98.69	99.77	99.84		99.97	99.98	99.95	99.96	99.97	99.85
	[70]	SNN	74.10	78.60	75.20	71.20	78.30	71.50	65.10	56.20	43.50	69.60	77.30
	Proposed	M ² VT	99.60	95.34	89.15	99.90	50.11	00.00	99.34	100.0	99.43	96.46	92.50
RC%	[53]	DNN	99.94	99.88	97.46	99.39		99.95	99.97	99.97	99.99	99.95	99.96
	[70]	SNN	78.90	66.20	70.50	74.90	54.20	73.20	55.30	60.30	48.30	70.10	45.30
	Proposed	M ² VT	99.96	87.97	96.93	99.91	99.90	00.00	98.03	99.88	98.33	92.31	97.66
F1%	[53]	DNN	99.94	99.28	98.60	99.62		99.96	99.97	99.96	99.98	99.96	99.90
	[70]	SNN	76.00	71.00	72.00	73.00	64.00	73.00	59.00	58.00	45.00	69.00	57.00
	Proposed	M ² VT	99.78	91.50	92.88	99.91	66.75	00.00	98.68	99.94	98.88	94.34	95.00

Fig. A16: Comparison of M²VT with conventional DL when performing Task 2 using the Edge-IIoT dataset

Fig. A17: Comparison of M²VT with Conventional DL when performing Task 3 using the Edge-IIoT dataset

TABLE A20: Comparison based on 15-class classification of Edge-IIoT dataset

Ref.	Method Name	AC%	PR%	RC%	F1%
[68]	Inception Time	94.94	98.30	92.40	95.30
[48]	J48	92.92	93.8	92.90	92.90
[69]	MLP	99.98	99.95	99.98	99.96
[65]	F-BIDS	90.93	88.06	92.20	89.00
[51]	DNN	94.67	80.02	77.00	77.34
[21]	Gradient boosting + tree	99.90			
Proposed	M ² VT	99.19	99.20	99.19	99.19

Fig. A18: Comparison of M²VT with Conventional DL when performing Task 3 using N-BaIoT dataset

Fig. A19: Comparison of M²VT with Conventional DL when performing Task 2 using testbed dataset

Fig. A20: Class-wise performance of the M²VT in the 8-Class classification on the UNSW-BoTIoT dataset

